

“BASIC APPROACHES, METHODS IN TEACHING DIALOGICAL SPEECH AS A TYPE OF SPEECH ACTIVITY WHEN TEACHING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TO FUTURE DIPLOMATS AND POLITICAL SCIENTISTS”

Atabekova Amina Bayrambekovna

Teacher of the Uzbek Department and Russian languages.

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Annotation This article examines and describes the methods, approaches and technology of professional teaching of the Russian language for future diplomats and political scientists. Particular attention is paid to the new approaches and methods necessary for teaching dialogic speech, organizing dialogue training, and teaching methods.

Key words: dialogue, dialogic speech, sphere of communication, teaching methods, business negotiations, professional communication, discussion.

Future diplomats and political scientists must learn to conduct a conversation in Russian, take part in discussions, speak publicly on topics in the social-political, professional, social and cultural spheres of communication, as well as correctly use speech etiquette.

We keep up with the times and therefore we cannot do without new methods, approaches and technologies in the educational process. The use of new methods and approaches helps in developing students' knowledge, skills and proficiency in the Russian language as a language of specialty for the purpose of its active use in the field of diplomacy, foreign policy and international relations.

For a future diplomat and political scientist, it is necessary to correctly use speech etiquette, which develops the ethics of international communication in students, improves the skills of independently acquiring and using professional knowledge and skills in international communication and business negotiations. Therefore, the most

important form of oral speech is dialogical speech. Therefore, students must first master dialogical speech. Dialogue speech is the most used form of verbal communication.

Speaking plays a major role in dialogical speech. The dialogue has a two-way character: one speaks, the other listens, but then the speaker and listener change roles, moving from one type of speech activity to another. To participate in a dialogue, you need the ability to speak and understand speech by ear, to develop listening, reading, speaking and writing skills. Teaching dialogical speech is created in the form of a dialogical text and the communication situation is determined. Dialogues are used by the partners' ability to conduct dialogue on a specific topic.

Let's look at the following types of dialogue that are necessary when used in the professional sphere.

1. Situational dialogue, dialogue - message, dialogue - questioning, dialogue - motivation. Choose a situation and role-play it.

2. Dialogue – conversation (conversation on a specific topic).

3. Dialogue – discussion.

The main methods of teaching dialogic speech are:

1. Presentation on this topic using technical teaching aids.

2. Expressions, phrases, lines in dialogue.

3. Playback the dialogue. Students should develop the following basic skills in oral dialogic speech.

Conduct a dialogue - conversation and dialogue - questioning using questioning, doubt, denial, agreement, condemnation, confirmation and approval.

And also conduct a dialogue - a discussion based on a text read or a film or video seen.

Students should also be able to give answers - reasoning to questions based on a text, film, video, and participate in dialogues - discussions (ask questions, refute someone else's point of view with reason and prove their own).

When teaching dialogical speech, you can use various forms of dialogues and forms of working with them: dialogue-conversation, pair and group forms of work, conversations between students and with the teacher. And also the use of the following techniques: 1) creating speech situations; 2) dramatization of dialogues. 3) role-playing games.

During the learning process, the skills are formed: to assimilate information, actively respond to the interlocutor's remarks, use various speech phrases and expressions on the topic, compose and combine remarks when constructing a dialogue.

At the initial stage of training, attention is paid to such types of dialogue as dialogue of an etiquette nature, dialogue-questioning, dialogue - an incentive to action, dialogue - exchange of information and opinions.

Dialogical speech is the construction and formulation of one's own thoughts and expression of one's opinion, the active maintenance of any conversation in communicative situations of informal and official communication.

Fundamentals of public speech (oral communication, report).

Professional communication is very important as the foundation for training future specialists in the field of international relations, which is formed on the basis of a training model and is based on the implementation of professional, systemic, activity-based, and other approaches.

From this we conclude that language learning is most effectively carried out in the process of speech activity, verbal communication, and with a communicative approach. During the learning process, students have the opportunity to develop communicative competence and use language in connection with the situation, which is especially important when teaching dialogical speech.

List of used literature.

1. Vasilyeva I.G., Ioannesyan V.A. Russian language. A guide to speech development: Textbook. Benefit for national groups of environments specialist. textbook establishments. – M.: Higher. school, 1987.

2. Issues of methodology for teaching Russian to non-Russians. Sat. articles by university teachers. Issue seven. – M., 1960.
3. Vilchek E. E. Exercises for mastering the elements of dialogic speech on a functional basis // Foreign language at school. – 1962. – No. 3. – P. 66-73. 4.
4. Varkovitskaya L. A. Work on replicas of dialogical speech / Varkovitskaya L. A. // Russian language in the national school. – 1969. – No. 4. – P. 19-26.
5. Russian language in national school. Problems of linguodidactics / Ed. N.M. Shansky, N.Z. Bakeeva. – M.: Pedagogy, 1997.
6. Methods of teaching the Russian language in national secondary school: Proc. manual for pedagogical students. Institute / Ed. N.Z. Bakeeva and Z.P. Daunene. – L.: LO Enlightenment, 1980.
7. Rosenbaum S. M. Fundamentals of teaching dialogical speech at the language faculty of pedagogical universities / Jerzy Maximilianovich Rosenbaum. – M.: Higher School, 1975. – 125 p. 8.
8. Diplomatic protocol and etiquette of business communication / P. F. Lyadov. M., 2012.
9. “Training materials on the Russian language for foreign students of 1-2 years of the specialty international relations.” Vasilyeva, T.V., Elnikova, S.I., Shorunova N.G. – M., RUDN Publishing House, 2001 5
10. Modern model of diplomacy. / T. V. Zonova. M., 2003.